

Effects of Social Media Platforms on the Performance of Small Scale Businesses (SSBs) in Gombe State

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Abstract

The growing concern on the issue of Business performance is one of the fundamentals facing Small Scale Businesses (SSBs) in Nigeria, as these SSBs accounted for 76% of total employment and provides 48.78% of national GDP. Upon these, the sector is facing significant barriers due to systemic and structural challenges such as; high failure rate with approximately 80% of SMEs closing within the first five years. On this note, SMEs' Problems were viewed by government to have originated from lack of; or inadequate capital rather than poor marketing orientation (MO) which include; innovativeness and pro-activeness toward utilizing opportunities that come alongside with technology, as key drivers of success in today's business world. This study examined the effect of Social Media Platforms on Business Performance of SSBs in Gombe State. Survey design was used, with the aid of structured questionnaire in collecting the required data conveniently from a sample of 264 respondents from the three senatorial zones of the State comprising of; Billiri, Akko, and Gombe Local Government each of which represent; Gombe South, Gombe central and Gombe North respectively. The collected data were analyzed using AMOS SEM with the aid of SPSS Version 23.0 to obtained the desired results. Four set of Hypotheses were raised and answered based on the research findings. Findings from the study indicated that, two of the hypotheses rejected the Null and appeared significant toward influencing Business Performance in Gombe State, while Youtube and Tiktok accepted the Null hypotheses and were both significant towards the Dependent variable. Moreover, it was recommended that, government mechanisms should be used in addressing the challenges anchored by Small Scale Businesses (SSBs) in Nigeria and in Gombe state to be precise, by providing more accessible technological infrastructures and affordable Social Media Platforms that promote Business activities of SSBs in Gombe State, for effective and efficient service delivery to people, mostly living in locations where physical marketing serve as a threat to lives and properties of the people.

Keywords: Social Media, Business performance, Gombe state, Nigeria.

Introduction

In recent decades, the proliferation of Small Scale Businesses (SSBs) has significantly impacted economic landscape globally. They are recognized as one of the main contributors to job creation, innovation, poverty reduction, economic development, fostering creativity and innovation. According to the World Bank (2021) report, SSBs account for approximately 90% of all businesses worldwide and contribute up to 50% of global employment. The resilience of small businesses is particularly evident in developing economies, where they accounted for 60 to 70% contribution to GDP, (International Finance Corporation, 2022). Their survival activities emphasized through prudent management of their marketing activities so as to sustain customer patronages and likewise to create a sustained financial stability has given the sector a recognition in economic growth and attainment of developmental objectives.

In Nigeria, as one of the developing countries in the globe, there were approximately over 41 million MSMEs (SMEDAN 2024). This MSMEs constitutes about 96% of all businesses nationally, and majority are Small-Scale Businesses. As far as the development of the rural and urban areas in Nigeria is concerned, the role of Small Scale Enterprises cannot be under-estimated. The subsector provides 48.78% of national GDP, accounting for 76% of total

employment and 76.64% of total exports (SMEDAN, 2024). SSBs play a vital role in Nigeria's economy, yet they struggle to survive. However, the performance of Small Scale businesses (SSBs) in Nigeria faces significant barriers due to systemic and structural challenges. A high failure rate plagues the sector, with approximately 80% of SMEs closing within the first five years, a trend mainly due to economic constraints, complex regulatory frameworks, and limited access to critical resources (MSME Africa, 2023).

According to Sayfullah, (2021); Angarini, (2021); Raja et al., (2023), & Rustan, (2024), all around the world, Small Scale Businesses (SSBs) play a crucial role in making significant contributions to economic growth. According to Esator et'al (2025), SMEs' Performance referred to how best they achieve their business objectives, often measured through financial and operational metrics like revenue growth, profitability, employment growth, and innovation. According to Hussain et al. (2020), SMEs' Performance is shaped by internal factors such as leadership, financial resources, and innovation capabilities, as well as external influences like market conditions and government policies.

In an effort to enhance the entire SMEs performance and to address challenges, the Nigerian government has introduced several policies and programs aimed at supporting their growth and resilience. Several programmes like Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises Development Fund (MSMEDF), Small and Medium Enterprises Equity Investment Scheme (SMEEIS), Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN). Bank of Industry (BOI) NIRSAL Microfinance Bank amongst others. These were complemented with several access-to-credit schemes of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and other Development Finance Institutions (DFIs). On this note, SMEs' Problems were viewed by government to have originated from lack of; or inadequate capital rather than poor marketing orientation (MO), which encompasses innovativeness, pro-activeness, and risk-taking as key drivers of business success.

The lack of a strong marketing orientation could hinder SMEs' ability to adapt to market dynamics and compete effectively. Despite these obstacles, digital transformation has empowered Small enterprises as 43% of Global Businesses now use advanced technologies (e.g., e-commerce platforms, AI tools) to enhance productivity (OECD, 2023). Moreover, technology is a valuable resource that creates opportunities, as customers can easily find products based on their interests by searching various vendors on the retailer's outreach. It was reported that, there is a significant positive correlation between Business performance and the use of digital technology (Zhe & Hamid, 2021). Social media as one of the instruments of digital marketing platforms (such as; Facebook, WhatsApp, Youtube, Instagram, Telegram to mention but a few) create awareness via online meetings.

The rise of social media has led to many innovations for businesses & entrepreneurs, allowing them to reach vast audiences at a fraction of a cost (Romanowski et al., 2019). Social media is currently used by over 4.6 billion people globally, and this number is predicted to increase to 5.8 billion users by 2027 (Statista, 2022). Majority of consumers are going online for their purchases as Ahmad, Ahmad, and Bakar (2018) discloses that, social media is a potential platform and strategy for increasing market coverage, it competitiveness, to improve business and customer relationship, and likewise information sharing. Studies have examined the impact of Social Media Platforms on various aspects of Business performance (Ndife (2020), Hachimi, et al (2021), Kateri (2021), MAAN, and RANIA (2021), Lateefat and Joshua (2023), Retno et al., (2024). These studies highlighted the significance of social media platforms in fostering business performance and financial outcomes.

However, the underutilization of social media as a marketing tool by Small scale businesses (SSBs) despite it numerous benefits, many SSBs are either unaware of the potential applications of social media or are unable to effectively utilize it for marketing purposes. Phillips Consulting, (2024) emphasized that, the inability to leverage digital transformation by SMEs, further hampers their global competitiveness, stunting Nigeria's economic development. This study is driven by the experiences of small business owners in the North East, Nigeria who utilize social media platforms as a means to enhance their business performance. This study assessed the effects of social media platforms. By comprehensively assessing these aspects, the study shed lights on the effectiveness of the platforms on the performance of SSBs and to provide practical recommendations in addressing the challenges faced by small businesses in the research location.

Small Scale Businesses

The concept of small-scale business is not new. Micro, Small and medium scale enterprises have existed for quite some centuries and since then have taken or assumed so many names like cottage industries, small and medium scale enterprises, (SME) micro, small and medium scale enterprises (MSME), Small Business Firms (SBF), small scale industries (SSI), small scale enterprises (SSE) etc. The issue of what constitutes a small scale business is a major concern in the literature. Most small businesses, however, are truly small. A small scale enterprise is a business which function on small scale level that is not large, in terms of its size, scope of operation, financial involvement and the workforce involved. In the commercial world, there are numerous kinds of business undertakings.

This definition is used in various CBN circulars and intervention programs, although the exact employee number can sometimes extend up to 200 in some contexts. The Nigeria Statistical Service (NSS) considers businesses with fewer than 10 employees as small scale businesses and their counterparts with more than 10 employees as medium and large-sized

business. However, the National Board for Small Scale Industries (NBSSI) in Nigeria applies both the “fixed asset and number of employees” criteria. It defines a small scale business as a business with not more than 9 workers, and has plant and machinery (excluding land, buildings and vehicles) not exceeding 10 million naira. Osei and Ogoni (2013) classified small scale businesses into three categories: micro businesses employing less than 6 people, small employing between 6 and 29 employees. Teal (2002), classified micro business less than 5 employees, small business 5-29 employees, medium business 30–99 employees and large business 100 and more employees. It is clear from the various definitions that there is not a general consensus over what constitutes an SSB.

Social Media

The meaning of the word ‘social media’ can be derived from two terms which constitute it. “Social media” as a term originated from Matisse, a Tokyo online media environment in 1994, and it has stuck ever since. Literature offers a variety of definitions for social media, as Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) described it as “a group of Internet based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0, and that allow the creation and exchange of user-generated contents. The types of social media include: social networks (Facebook, WhatsApp, Myspace, and LinkedIn), micro-blogs (Twitter, Instagram, Plurk, and Friend Feed), reviews and ratings (Yelp, Amazon, and Trip Advisor), video (YouTube, TikTok and Vimeo), and other social media websites are collectively referred to as social media.

Social platforms facilitate socializing with friends and family, online dating, professional networking, and many other forms of engagement, including engagement between small businesses and their customers or markets. Social media have more than 100,000,000 registered users. (Aichner, 2021). Users typically access social media services via web-based technologies on desktop computers, and laptops, or download services that offer social media functionality to their mobile devices (e.g., smartphones and tablet computers). Social Media is growing every day. 90% of the 18-24 internet users use social network via any device at least once per month, social media affects every age group with much higher increase rates for the age groups over 35 (Hubspot, 2012).

Also, when looking at the average hours per week spent on online activities, we can definitely see that the world is becoming more social, with an average of 4.6 hours per week spend on Social Media Sites worldwide. According to Nielsen, internet users continue to spend more time with social media sites than any other type of site. Furthermore, users can find a lot of free social media. Based on the nature of the social media, it can also easily do the selling, advertising, and marketing for business using a ready tool (Ainin et al., 2015). The fact that it is been widely used in the developing countries as a tool for marketing, SMEs in Nigeria can make maximum use of it for serving customers well and competitiveness.

Small Scale Business Performance

Performance standards are a key component of every firm, whether public or private as it highlights the degree of the firm accomplishment of its objectives. The measurement of SME performance often includes both financial indicators such as Sales growth, profit growth, revenue and growth and non-financial indicators, including customer satisfaction, quality of services provided, and how to satisfy customers’ needs and employee engagement (Khan et al., 2022). Financial performance is a subjective measure of how well a firm can use assets from its primary mode of business and generate revenue. The term is also used as a general measure of a firm's overall financial health over a given period. According to Jesse et al (2019) financial performance is the achievement of the company's financial performance for a certain period covered the collection and allocation of finance measured by capital adequacy, liquidity, solvency, efficiency, leverage and profitability.

Among the various methods available for measuring business performance, objective and subjective methods are commonly used in academic literature. The objective methods can be quantified whereas the subjective methods are mostly qualitative (Yıldız & Karakaş, 2012; Vij & Bedi, 2016). Nevertheless, it has proved rather difficult to agree on a common definition of it as well as a method to measure it (Yıldız & Karakaş, 2012). The State of the art of this study is based on improving the marketing performance of small scale businesses in Gombe State. Therefore, the current study will focus on objective measures (non-financial performance) in explaining SSBs performance. This study view business performance as how well small scale businesses (SSBs) achieve their business objectives, often measured through marketing performance base like customer satisfaction, sales growth and market share over a given period of time.

Social Media and Small Scale Business Performance

The conceptual framework in figure 1 lays out the key factors, construct, or variables and presumes relationships among them. For the purpose of this study, the dependents variable is identified as business performance which will be measured by customer satisfaction, market share, and sales growth respectively, while the dependent variables are social media platforms proxies by facebook, whatsApp, Instagram, Youtube and Tiktok. The goals of socias media platforms is to maximize the overall performance of small scale businesses. Social media offers a variety of free or lowcost solutions to be used effectively SMEs (Odoom et al. 2023)

Facebook and SSBs Performance

Facebook is a social networking site that can allow people to connect and chat in the same community. Facebook which is founded by a computer programmer- Mark Zuckerberg while studying at Harvard University in February, 2004 (Chheda, 2014). It can connect individuals, reunite people with old friends, create opportunity for new relationships to be established and generate trust through word of mouth communication (Etuk and Udoh, 2020). In 2015, Facebook site had 1.45 billion active users in the world, with more than 1.55 billion active users as of 2016 (Ladokun, 2019). As at June 2017, Facebook was the largest and most powerful social media platform in the world with over 2 billion monthly active subscribers and the rate of growth continued at 20 million active users per month (Statista, 2019).

In the aspect of business perspective, since the emergence of Facebook, business practitioners and managers have adopted it for the promotion of their businesses. Estimates reports that over 90 million businesses have active pages on the platform as a result of the population of users across different platforms through the use of marketing tools (Kateri, 2021). Facebook and Instagram have become the go-to platforms for small businesses to present their content, especially through features like Reels. A notable global trend highlights the significance of Reels, with 47% of consumers utilizing this feature to discover and explore new products (Desalu, 2023).

In Nigeria, as of early 2025, Nigeria had approximately 38.7 million Facebook users, representing about 16.3% of the country's total population (Datareportal, 2025). A research carried out in Nigeria by Morning Consult Brand Intelligence revealed that small and medium enterprises in Nigeria benefit from placing adverts for Facebook users to view. Facebook users claim they visit a page at least once a week. Prospective customers in Nigeria nowadays prefer making purchases via Facebook because they perceived it to be very reliable compared to other social media platform (Osugwu, 2017).

WhatsApp and SSBs Performance

WhatsApp is a free social media app for mobile phones launched in 2009. It is a mobile instant messaging (MIM) application (Balarabe, 2020). It enables smart phone users, with the convenience of a mobile data plan, to send and receive text messages to individuals or groups of people. WhatsApp, simply put, is a free social app used in sharing text, pictures, voice and video using the Internet. It uses the phone's internet connection to allow chatting as well as sharing of files and images and permits the making of free voice and video calls with other WhatsApp users. Initially, it was for mobile phones only. Later on, the web version of the app was introduced (Mazereeuw, 2018; Dove, 2020).

A cell phone might be used to contact 1,000 people if there were four of these kinds of groupings. According to Lawal et al. (2022), the introduction of WhatsApp birthed new features on social media, especially its effectiveness in commercial activities. Mgbeahurike (2015) asserts that a single concept can approach or reach one million individuals in just a few shares. WhatsApp applications have appealing functions like Share, Tag, Comment, Like, Smiley, and more that appeal to a wide variety of age groups. WhatsApp (a pun on the phrase "what's up"), with 1.5 billion monthly active users around the world, prides itself as the leading social media platform in most parts of the world (Mazereeuw, 2018). The number of WhatsApp users across the world are about 2 billion as of 2020 (Noor et al., 2017). The number has been increasing tremendously every two years. Statista reported that 1.6 billion users access the messaging app each month (Statista 2019) which is 23 percent above its closest competitor.

Research has shown that small business growth in the era of digital revolution is made possible by WhatsApp. This is the reason Bhat (2021) added that accessibility to company's product is no longer an issue due to the support of social media platforms such as WhatsApp. In furtherance, Shetty (2020) asserted that the flexibility of WhatsApp in terms of video and voice. Several studies (Ghanem & Hamid, 2020; Syaifullah, et al 2021; Atah & Abang, 2022) have showed that social media (including WhatsApp) not only has a positive impact on business performance but also enhance the prospects go transforming the business model. Businesses receive location information, images and audio visual materials (Oji, 2016), at little or no cost.

YouTube and SSBs Performance

According to Woletz (2008), YouTube is a video-sharing service that lets users upload files to YouTube servers, where they are available online. In February of 2005, Steve Chen, Chad Hurley, and Jawed Karim founded YouTube (Varga, 2009). The site was created as a forum for people to create and share short video clips online and rank among the most successful Web 2.0 platforms or tools. (Varga, 2009). Among the features of YouTube include; allowing users to view, upload, comment, subscribe, and join groups, when viewing a video, viewers can see the title of the video, the description of the video, who uploaded the video, date and time of upload, and tags specified by the owner. More than 100 million videos are streamed daily on YouTube. On YouTube, videos are shared by journalists, travelers, food bloggers, producers, and directors, and collect responses and feedback from the community. With the help of YouTube, opportunities are expressed in video format; making content available to anyone interested in consuming it occasionally.

An understanding of the role of social media, especially YouTube, in the context of marketing and business growth is very necessary. In 2006, YouTube first presented several advertising concepts to companies for utilizing the platform as an effective marketing tool. Moreover, it is related to the concept of empowering MSMEs through social media, with a

focus on YouTube as a potential marketing tool. With the growth of YouTube, marketers are fast connecting to the site. Compared to the traditional media advertising site, YouTube is completely different by offering new contacts and community building possibilities. Eventually, these changes resulted in YouTube to become one of the leading influencer marketing platforms besides Instagram, Facebook, and Snapchat (Carter, 2016; Jackson 2018). YouTube today provides multiple advertising formats such as displays ads, skippable and non-skippable video ads (YouTube Help, 2018).

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TikTok and SSBs Performance

TikTok was launched in China by the Chinese technology company ByteDance. It was launched as Douyin in China in September 2016, but it was later spread to various countries, including Nigeria, under the name TikTok in September 2017. And since then, it has experienced rapid growth worldwide. TikTok is a mobile application that has allowed innumerable users to entertain themselves by creating, watching videos, and promoting businesses through short video content. Now, it is in many countries and languages. The app is a new type of MSN that has reached 689 million monthly active users worldwide (Moshin, 2021). Moreover, the number of TikTok users increases rapidly year by year, and the monthly number of active users is more than 800 million. The TikTok app has a great opportunity to enable its users to become creators and encourage the sharing of creative expression and content through short videos.

TikTok’s social media marketing has a substantial impact on purchase intention by increasing brand recognition and exposure. Users discover a wide variety of content while scrolling through their TikTok feeds, including commercials from companies. TikTok's features are optimally utilized and approached effectively with consumers, it can help drive sales (Nufus & Handayani, 2022) TikTok can assist in marketing products and increasing sales, many advertisers and marketers utilize video-sharing platforms that serve as one of their social media advertising and marketing promotional tools and their functions to promote their products. (Lee, Kim, Ham, and Kim, 2016). As long as the content appeals to the audience, engagement will follow so marketers can achieve significant buzz with carefully planned campaigns and compelling content. Therefore, entrepreneurs need to pay attention to how they promote their products through images and detailed information attached to describe the product clearly (Aji et al., 2022).

Conceptual Model

Based on the previous literature reviewed, several possible efforts were made by researchers in relation with the determinants of Business performance using Social Media Platforms in Nigeria and beyond. Figure 1 below, represent the conceptual framework of the study showing the relationship between Business performance as the dependent variable, and its determinants as the independent variable that appear mostly in Social Media Platforms literatures in relation with Business performance.

Figure 1: Adapted from the works of; IHEMEJE, 2021; UMAR, et’al, 2022; SRIVASTAVA, 2023 & NUR 2024).

Social Marketing Theory (SMT)

The theory had its roots in the 1970s when marketing techniques were realized to sell ideas, attitudes and behaviours rather than products. Social Marketing Theory, emphasizes the use of social media platforms to influence target audiences (Nansel, 2022). The framework will be utilized to understand effects of social media platforms on the performance of small scale businesses. The theory was proposed by Philip Kotler and Gerald Zaltman, which is now being used by social and welfare organizations (Shraddha, 2018). Their definition includes social marketing as "the process of applying marketing principles and techniques to create, communicate, and deliver value in order to influence the behaviors of target audiences in a socially beneficial way." (Public health, safety, environment and community) as

well as the target audience". (Kotler et al., 2012). The main focus of this theory is on consumer behaviors and attitudes. It also integrates principles, marketing ideas, tools, socially beneficial concepts and techniques to promote communication and benefit society. It is almost impossible today to find a society unaffected by electronic media, the media enjoys tremendous attention and audience, and It is estimated according to comScore's 2017 cross platform future in focus report, a third of earth's population spend over 17% of their time on their media devices and in turn over 70% of the time spent on these media devices are spent on social media. The study tries to find out how exploitation of these facts have improved the growth of businesses in Nigeria for Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, YouTube and TikTok in particular.

The significant of this theory to the study that it integrates principles, marketing ideas, tools, socially beneficial concepts and techniques to promote communication and benefit society.

Methodology of the study

The study was intended to establish the effects of social media platforms (Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube and TikTok) on Marketing Performance (Customer satisfaction, Sales growth, and Market share) of small scale businesses. Survey design was used to obtain information that describes existing phenomena by asking registered business owners in Gombe State, where the number of employees in each business ranges from 11 and above. The research has a population size of seven hundred and seventy-Nine (779) registered businesses in Gombe State with approximately 16,100 staff strength. With the aid of structured questionnaire used stratified and conveniently collected from a sample of 264 SSBs from the three senatorial districts of the State (Gombe North, Gombe Central and Gombe South) deduced using Taro Yamane formula (1974), measured using 5 Likert Scale. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the demographic data of the respondents, while Analysis of Moment Structure (AMOS) SEM was used in analyzing the psychological data with the aid of SPSS version 23.0 respectively.

Analysis and Results

Confirmatory factor analysis was conducted in the entire construct to determine the measures which indicated the validity, unidimensionality and reliability of the measurement models prior to modelling the Structural Equation Model. Square multiple correlation was used to show the strength and to enable the weaker items to be dropped from, or covariates based on the modification indices result of the construct under consideration. While multiple correlation indicates the strength of the relationship between the exogenous construct and endogenous construct (Ganguli & Roy, 2011; Al-majali, 2011; Zainudin, 2012). The construct validity was achieved as the Cronbach's alpha values were 0.6 or higher for all the components and for the fitness indexes; GFI were 0.90 and higher, CFI were 0.90 and higher, RMSEA were less than 0.08 and CMIN were less than 5.0 based on the criterion propounded by Awang, 2012.

Figure 2 below, is a reflection of the items which indicated a reliable measure. The factor loadings were all within the required threshold of 0.6 and above, while the square of multiple correlation were also within the limit of 0.4 and above (Awang, 2012).

Figure 2:

Source: AMOS Output, Version 23.0 (2025)

As shown in figure 2 above, all the index criteria were met. This was achieved after model re-specifications by either freeing off a parameter or deleting any of the items from the model that fall below the required threshold.

Table:1 Assessment of the fitness Indexes of the entire Constructs.

Name of category	Name on index	Index Value	Comments
Absolute fit	RMSEA	0.041	Required level achieved
Absolute fit	GFI	0.961	Required level achieved
Incremental fit	CFI	0.973	Required level achieved
Parsimonious fit	ChiSq/df	4.809	Required level achieved

Source: AMOS Output, Version 23.0 (2025)

The factor loadings for all items in the CFA is considered appropriate and has a good fit, thus ready to be subjected into SEM Analysis.

Figure: 3

Source: AMOS Output, Version 23.0 (2025)

Table:2 Assessment of fitness for the final Structural Model Equation

Name of category	Name on index	Index Value	Comments
Absolute fit	RMSEA	0.038	Required level achieved
Absolute fit	GFI	0.961	Required level achieved
Incremental fit	CFI	0.944	Required level achieved
Parsimonious fit	ChiSq/df	4.667	Required level achieved

Source: AMOS Output, Version 23.0 (2025)

Table:3 Hypothesis testing for the causal effect of all the construct

Path relationship	Estimate	S.E.	C.R	P. V	Remark
FB → MP	.676	.099	6.8	.521	Rejected
WA → MP	.040	.049	.82	.412	Rejected
YT → MP	.434	.068	6.3	***	Supported
TT → MP	1.033	.071	14	***	Supported

Source: AMOS SEM Output Version 23.0 (2025)

The hypotheses tested using CFA SEM path modelling results, Rejected Hypothesis I and it shows a significant relationship toward influencing Marketing performance with a ($\beta= 0.676$; $CR= 6.8$; $P= 0.521$). This simply mean that, all other variables held constant, Facebook usage by SSBs predict Business performance by 21%, which appeared in the hypotheses tested to have rejected the Null and accepted the Alternate. Hypothesis II was highly significant toward predicting Business performance by 71% which rejected the Null and accepted the Alternate according to the findings; as it ($\beta= 0.40$; $CR= 0.82$; $P= 0.412$), this mean that, the services provided by SSBs through WhatsApp is to some extent reliable as the result indicated. While Youtube and Tiktok (Hypothesis III & IV) were both supported with a ($\beta= 0.434$; $CR= 6.3$; $P= 0.00$ & $\beta= 1.033$; $CR= 14.0$; $P= 0.00$ respectively). The result as shown, Youtube and Tiktok in Gombe state do not properly predict Business performance of SSBs even though, they are both significant toward influencing the Business performance with 77% and 65% contribution respectively.

On a general note, the value of R^2 for the entire contributions of the Four (4) factors studied on Business Performance of SSBs in Gombe state is 66%. As this research has gotten these contributions on the dependent variable specifically on Facebook, WhatsApp, Youtube and Tiktok, this suggested that, other variables other than the Four Social Media indicators used in this work can as well be explored that may have significant contribution to Business Performance of SSBs in Gombe State.

Conclusion and recommendation

This research work, provides an overview of some of the influential Social Media platforms that predicts Business performance of SSBs in Gombe state. It addresses issues related to Small Scale Business performance in the most attractive mode of Social Media platforms in used. As government mechanisms is inadequate/fail to address the challenges anchored by SSBs in Nigeria and in Gombe state to be precise, by providing more accessible and likewise affordable infrastructures for effective and efficient service delivery to people living in locations where physical marketing serve as a threat to lives and properties of the people.

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References

- Adebisi, T., Adeyemi, F., & Ayodele, O. (2023). SMEs' contribution to Nigeria's GDP and employment. *African Economic Review*, 18(1), 12–25.
- Aikor, S., & Timothy C. (2021). Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs): Key to Socio-Economic. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)* |Vol. 5 (12), ISSN 2454-6186
- Balarabe, U. B. (2020). Survey on the Usage of Whatsapp and Instagram Social Media as Advertising Tools. *South Asian Academic Research Journals*. Vol. 10 (4). Pp. 226- 232
- Baker, W. E., & Barlow, J. M. (2022). Innovation and agility in SMEs: Drivers of competitive performance in dynamic markets. *Entrepreneurship Research Journal*, 12(3), 345–367. <https://doi.org/10.1515/erj-2020-0254>
- Cho-I P. & Young N. (2022). The Effects of Instagram Marketing Activities on Customer-Based. <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/14/3/1657><https://doi.org/10.3390/su14031657>
- Dar, Q. A., Ahmad, F., Ramzan, M., Khan, S. H., Ramzan, K., Ahmed, W., & Kamal, Z. (2017). Use of social media tool “Whatsapp” in medical education. *Annals of King Edward Medical University*, 23(1).
- Rabia Noor and Huma Zafar (2024) Influence of Instagram Reels on Marketing Tactics of Small Businesses https://irnbrjournal.com/paper_details.php?id=1237
- Desalu, O. (2023). Getting Reel: A Quantitative Analysis of Facebook & Instagram Reel Usage Among Small, Independent Clothing Boutiques in Fayetteville, Arkansas. Retrieved from <https://scholarworks.uark.edu/mktguht/72>

9. Esator, G. O., Adio, A. K., Adeniyi, A. A., & Ikediasor, E. F. (2025). Dynamic capabilities and organizational performance of selected micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in Lagos State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Social Sciences and Strategic Management Techniques*, 11(1), 170-193. [10.48028/iiprds/ijirssmt.v11.i1.09](https://doi.org/10.48028/iiprds/ijirssmt.v11.i1.09)
10. Fedianty A., Andry H., Sandra O., Liling L. & Damajanti S. L. (2024). *International Journal of Economics, Business and Management Research* https://ijebmr.com/uploads/pdf/archivepdf/2024/IJEBMR_1487.pdfURL: <https://doi.org/10.51505/IJEBMR.2024.81117>
11. Gombe Population (2025). *World Population Review*. Retrieved May 18, 2025, from <https://worldpopulationreview.com/cities/nigeria/gombe>
12. Guerrero, & Katherine J., (2023). "An Analysis of TikTok's Digital Marketing Capabilities and Its Effectiveness for Brands and Businesses Across Different Industries". Theses. 532. <https://digitalcommons.lindenwood.edu/theses/532>
13. International Monetary Fund. (2024). Financing barriers and performance of micro, small, and medium enterprises, *IMF Staff Country Reports*, 2024(271). <https://www.elibrary.imf.org/view/journals/002/2024/271/article-A002-en.xml>
14. Magarura R., Olutayo K. O., & Samuel O. W. A. (2024). How Facebook adaptation impacts SMEs performance. https://journal.adpebi.com/index.php/AIJB/article/view/787?utm_source=perplexity<https://doi.org/10.54099/aijb.v3i1.787>
15. Moshin, M. (2021, February). 10 TikTok Statistics you Need to Know. Oberlo. <https://www.oberlo.com/blog/tiktok-statistics#:~:text=TikTok%20has%20689%20million%20monthly%20active%20users%20worldwide.>
16. Moh. Ilham, Sudarmiatina, & Ludi Wishnu Wardana (2023). The Success of Viral Videos on YouTube as a Growth Driver for MSMEs (Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises) <https://journal.formosapublisher.org/index.php/fjst/article/view/6990><https://doi.org/10.55927/fjst.v2i11.6990>
17. Phillips Consulting. (2024, January 18). Empowering Nigeria's Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs): Overcoming challenges for economic prosperity. <https://phillipsconsulting.net/newsroom/empowering-nigerias-small-andmedium-enterprises-smes-overcoming-challenges-for-economic-prosperity>
18. Retno Budi Lestari, Sulastri*, Muchsin Saggaff Shihab, Isni Andriana, (2024), "Social Media Marketing and Its Impact on SMEs' Business Performance" in 8th Sriwijaya Economics, Accounting, and Business Conference, KnE Social Sciences, pages 503–515. DOI 10.18502/kss.v9i14.16121
19. Romanowski, R., Lewicki, M., & Ciechowski, W. (2019). Managing Economic Innovations – Methods and Instruments. In *Managing Economic Innovations – Methods and Instruments* (Issue September). <https://doi.org/10.12657/9788379862771>
20. Shamsudin, Mohd Farid, Esa, S. A., & Ali, A. M. (2019). Determinants of customer loyalty towards the hotel industry in Malaysia. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 6(9), 21–29.
21. Syaifullah, J., Syaifudin, M., Sukendar, M. U., & Junaedi, J. (2021). Social media marketing and business performance of MSMEs during the COVID-19 pandemic. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(2), 523-531
22. SMEDAN (2020). *SMEDAN and National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) National Survey of NANO, Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (NMSMEs)*.
23. Son, J., & Niehm, L. (2020). Using Social Media to Navigate Changing Rural Markets: The Case of Small Community Retail and Service Businesses. *Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship*, 33, 619-637. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08276331.2021.1871711>
24. Wantchami, N.L., Ngange, N.L., & Efosi, B.D. (2020). Investigated the nexus of social media marketing and small scale businesses performance in Buea, Cameroon. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 7(2).
25. YouTube Help. (2018). YouTube advertising formats. Google LLC. Retrieved from <https://support.google.com/youtube/answer/2467968?hl=en>
26. Zhe, B. O. M., & Hamid, N. A. (2021). The impact of digital technology, digital capability, and digital innovation on small business performance. *Research in Management of Technology and Business*, 2(1), 499–509.